

FEATURES OF LIQUID PHASE DISPERSION INTO A PSEUDO-FLUID LAYER DURING SEED TREATMENT

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Abstract

Modern methods of preparing seed grain with high energy potential are considered, including pickling, calibration, encrustation and coating. Trends in the development of the global market of seed coating materials, in particular polymers, dyes and chemical treatment agents, are analyzed. The feasibility of using heterogeneous jet-pulsation fluidization to increase the efficiency of heat and mass transfer and preserve seed quality is substantiated. The influence of the geometry of the granular material and temperature restrictions on the uniformity of irrigation and avoidance of overheating is determined. The use of peat as a carrier of microorganisms, mineral nutrients and stimulants is proposed, the composition of which is determined by the agro-ecological and climatic conditions of their use. According to previous studies, the most appropriate for dispersion is the use of a rotary mechanical disperser with the introduction of the liquid phase in a pulsation mode corresponding to the frequency of pulsations of the jet-pulsation mode of fluidization.

Keywords: seed material, seed treatment, seed dressing, incrustation, pelleting, calibration, fluidization, jet-pulsating mode, disperser, granulator, microorganisms, seed energy potential, thermolability.

Introduction.

The increasing demands for precision nutrition and biostimulation of wheat seeds, restrictions on pesticide treatments and the drive to save on fertilizers stimulate the search for breathable multilayer coatings with controlled water and gas exchange. The most controllable and scalable way to form such coatings is to apply in a fluidized bed with spraying of the liquid phase inside the layer (Wurster/bottom-spray, other schemes), where hydrodynamics and dispersion determine the quality of the coating, the risk of agglomeration and the thermal load on the living grain. Modern studies confirm that the nozzle position, droplet size, spray flow rate and gas velocity critically affect the uniformity of the layer and the continuity of the process; in parallel, interest in nutrient/biological coatings for wheat (stress resistance, fertilizer efficiency) is growing. The problem of matching dispersion with "living" seed limitations (oxygen, waterlogging, product temperature) remains unresolved at the level of reliable engineering criteria [5].

The global seed coating market (colorants, polymers, fillers and other additives) was worth US\$1.8 billion in 2019 and is expected to reach US\$3.0 billion by 2025. The main group of active ingredients are chemical seed treatments, estimated to be worth US\$3-5 billion in 2020, accounting for at least two-thirds of the total seed treatment market[7].

Effective methods for preparing seed with high energy potential include dressing, calibration, encrustation and coating [6].

Coating creates a controlled environment for initial growth (moisture, gas exchange, nutrients, protection), but for wheat, air and moisture permeability of the coating, avoidance of local overmoistening and overheating, and prevention of agglomeration are particularly critical. Known industrial schemes of liquid

introduction in fluidized bed devices - spraying over the bed, in the bed (ProCell type) and "Wurster" circulation - limit active volumetric activation and often implement an agglomeration mechanism, which in the case of heterogeneous suspensions and seeds increases the risk of stagnant zones and sticking. [3]

There are many ways to implement such processes, but the use of inhomogeneous jet-pulsation fluidization allows to increase at least up to 50% of the heat utilization while maintaining the driving force for heat and mass exchange throughout the volume of the initial granular bed in the granulator chamber.

An important factor for the successful implementation of the process is the uniform application of the liquid phase to the surface of the granular material, which has the shape of an ellipsoid with a symmetry axis ratio of 1/2 (Figure 1). This significantly affects the aerodynamics of the movement of granular material in the irrigation zone and increases the risk of local overwetting of the granular material cluster. The second significant factor in the implementation of the process is the thermolability of the seeds, which after thermal treatment should not lose their vegetative potential, therefore the temperature in the layer cannot exceed 40⁰ C (+,-).[9]

Also, to maximize the increase in nutrient components in the liquid phase, the authors [6] proposed applying peat as a means of delivering microorganisms. Thanks to this approach, the concentration of dry matter in the liquid phase will increase to 80%.

Therefore, it is advisable to use a mechanical rotary disperser for the introduction of the liquid phase [8]. Taking into account the frequency of pulsations in the layer, the liquid phase should be supplied in a pulsating mode when the porosity in the aureole of the rotary disperser is within 0.6 ϵ.

Compared to disk sprayers, a bowl disperser with lateral perforations significantly increases the volume of “effective” irrigation and provides stable kinetics of layered growth without agglomeration; in relevant studies for heterogeneous systems, high granulation coefficients and a multiple increase in productivity have been recorded precisely due to the increase in the irrigation area and recirculation through the bowl.[2]

Therefore, to eliminate these limitations, it is advisable to combine: heterogeneous jet-pulsation fluidization, which cyclically “scans” the layer and removes stagnation on the hydraulic fracturing (gas distribution grid) [1]; and a rotary bowl disperser with a perforated lateral surface, which many times increases the geometry of the irrigation area and forms a valve-like ejection of moistened particles into the volume of the layer with

their subsequent dilution with dry grains. This provides a layered mechanism without liquid “bridges” and agglomeration; the average droplet diameter in rational modes is $\leq 150\mu\text{m}$.

Results.

Based on previous experiments, we assume that the mass of the liquid is - 5% of the mass of the grain and further [6,10]

$$\frac{\pi d^3}{6} \rho_{liquid} = S_{liquid} m_{seed} \quad (1)$$

Where S_{liquid} – mass fraction of liquid from the mass of grain, %; ρ_{liquid} – density of liquid, kg/m^3 [2], d - equivalent diameter, m, m_{seed} – mass of one grain, kg.

With a grain mass of $4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg (Figure 1)

Fig. 1 – photo of grain size and mass

Where the mass of 10,000 drops of liquid is 5% of the mass of the grain.

Also, considering that for wheat (average values at humidity ~9%) the length, width and thickness (height) of the grain are:

Length (L) ≈ 7.5 mm, width (W) ≈ 3.4 mm, thickness / height (T) ≈ 2.7 mm [11,12], where the grain is an ellipsoid (Figure 2)

Fig. 2 – image of the semi-axes of an ellipsoid

$$a = \frac{L}{2} = \frac{7,46}{2} \approx 3,73 \text{ mm}, \quad b = \frac{W}{2} = \frac{3,37}{2} \approx 1,685 \text{ mm}, \quad c = \frac{T}{2} = \frac{2,66}{2} \approx 1,33 \text{ mm} \quad (2)$$

The grain plane, through Knud Thomsen's approximation, will be:

$$S \approx 4\pi \left(\frac{a^p b^p + a^p c^p + b^p c^p}{3} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (3)$$

where $p \approx 1,6075$ (empirical constant for all types of ellipsoids)

$$S \approx 4\pi \left(\frac{3,73^{1,6075} 1,685^{1,6075} + 3,73^{1,6075} 1,33^{1,6075} + 1,685^{1,6075} 1,33^{1,6075}}{3} \right)^{\frac{1}{1,6075}} \approx 5,9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$S \approx 59 \text{ mm}^2$$

Therefore, the thickness of the liquid film for 5% of the grain mass should be

$$V_{5\%} = \frac{S_{liquid} m_{seed}}{\rho_{liquid}} = \frac{0,05 \cdot 4 \cdot 10^{-5}}{1220} = 1,639 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3 \quad (5)$$

And with a uniform distribution of the liquid, the film thickness will be

$$t_{5\%} = \frac{V_{5\%}}{S} = \frac{1,639 \cdot 10^{-9}}{5,9 \cdot 10^{-5}} = 3,12 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m} \text{ або } 31 \mu\text{m} \quad (6)$$

It is planned to use a liquid phase with the addition of peat and mineral nutrient and stimulating components where the proportion of dry matter reaches 80% (mass) and 20% (mass) of water, which will evaporate in the process.

The working hypothesis is that to prevent agglomeration of granular material by forming liquid bridges, the droplet size should not exceed $50 \mu\text{m}$

This working hypothesis and the location of the disperser will be theoretically substantiated in the future.

Conclusions.

Therefore, it is proposed to carry out calculations and experimentally determine: the location of the disperser arrangement (zones I-III, placement and height of the bowl, perforation, linear edge velocity, pulsation periods, etc. [1]; and the effectiveness of the droplet size with dimensions $\leq 50 \mu\text{m}$ at a high proportion of dry matter. It is expected to obtain a uniform air-permeable shell on wheat grains without loss of viability, minimal agglomeration and stable process kinetics due to the increase in the irrigation area and control of the droplet size. The proposed arrangement is scalable and suitable for various coating formulations and crops.

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